

Reproducing Experimental Results from On Heavy-user Bias in A/B Testing

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ABSTRACT

The reproducibility of scientific papers has been a core concept of the scientific method as we know it today. But with a growing number of publications and an ever increasing palette of computer based research methods this reproducibility is becoming more difficult. We chose to examine the findings and reproducibility of the paper Yu Wang, Somit Gupta, Jiannan Lu, Ali Mahmoudzadeh, and Sophia Liu. 2019. On Heavy-user Bias in A/B Testing [2]. Reruns of the conducted simulations were performed and further thoughts about the experiment setup made.

KEYWORDS

A/B Testing, Reproducibility, Eternal validity

1 INTRODUCTION

The paper [2] discusses the heavy-user bias in A/B testing, which occurs by users frequently using a service in an A/B testing setting. The over representation of heavy users in the time limited test leads to a bias in the experiment. In the paper a bias-adjusted estimator for the *scaled single average* is proposed, which can reduce the heavy-user bias to a factor of $O(k^{-2})$, compared with the natural relation of $O(k^{-1})$ with k being the duration of the experiment in days. After introducing to the problem, the paper states three assumptions, from which the bias-adjusted estimator is derived. To verify the results an A/B testing experiment is simulated and the biased estimator, the bias-adjusted estimator and the block-bootstrap adjusted estimator is calculated. In a first step we will discuss the assumptions made and how plausible for real world applications they are. Then we will reproduce the simulation experiment and examine the parameters used for the simulation. In a last step we add another bias discussed in the paper to the simulation and investigate how this effects the performance of the adjusted-estimator.

2 ASSUMPTIONS

Vital to the derivation of the estimator three assumptions were made. Especially assumption 1 and 3, which are as stated below do severely limit the usefulness in real world applications.

Assumption 1 (stable unit treatment value assumption)

One user's outcome is unaffected by other user's treatment assignments. In other words, different users do not interfere with each other.

Assumption 3 (incremental experiment assumption)

We assume that for each user the activity indicator is independent of the treatment assignment.

These are quite restrictive assumptions, which was also touched upon in the paper [2]. The first assumption is violated by any kind of user user interaction, which limits its usefulness to services

Table 1: Reported biases with standard errors

Estimator	Simulation 1	Simulation 2
Bias of original estimator	0.0220 (0.0023)	0.0373 (0.0020)
Bias of jackknife adjusted estimator	-0.0022 (0.0026)	0.0132 (0.0023)
Bias of block-bootstrap adjusted estimator	0.0080 (0.0025)	0.0232 (0.0022)

Table 2: Reproduced biases with standard errors

Estimator	Simulation 1	Simulation 2
Bias of original estimator	0.0217 (0.0023)	0.0336 (0.0025)
Bias of jackknife adjusted estimator	-0.0019 (0.0026)	0.0085 (0.0027)
Bias of block-bootstrap adjusted estimator	0.0078 (0.0025)	0.0189 (0.0026)

where users can not interact with one another. The third assumption as mentioned in the paper implies that users do not change their frequency behaviour if they are in the treatment group. Both assumptions alone reduce the usefulness of real world applications which is shown with the following adjusted experiment simulations.

3 REPRODUCTION

3.1 Simulation Details

Two experiment simulations were performed in the paper [2]. The first one full filling the assumptions made, and the second one with a simulated novelty bias. Both simulated experiments where lasting for 14 days, with 1000 units per group. For each experiment data generation was performed 100 times and the mean and variance of the standard estimator, the bias-adjusted estimator and the block-bootstrap adjusted estimator were reported. The simulations were easily reproducible, as the code used for generating the experiments was made available via GitHub by the authors.

3.2 Reproducing Results

We run the simulations and compared the results to the ones reported in [2]. The reported values can be seen in Table 1 and our results in Table 2. We see, that the reported values are very similar to the ones we got from the reproduced simulation, even though the results are not exactly the same, as for both simulations a random seed was used.

3.3 Consistency of the Simulation

In order to see how consistent the results of the simulation are, a histogram of the spread of the means of 100 simulations was made. The histogram of the standard estimator can be seen in Figure 1 in the appendix, as well as those of the jackknife adjusted-estimator in Figure 2 and the bootstrap adjusted-estimator in Figure 3. As can

Table 3: Novelty Bias Testing

Estimators	$5 * U_u(t)$	$U_u(t)$
Continues Analysis	0.0469 (0.0024)	0.1291 (0.0024)
Jackknife Analysis	0.0210 (0.0028)	0.0984 (0.0027)
Bootstrap Analysis	0.0320 (0.0026)	0.1106 (0.0027)

be seen from the graphs the results of the paper [2] are within the region where most of the data is located. There are no real outliers as can be expected since the simulation itself already uses the mean of a 100 simulations. *For clarity: This means these graphs are the realization of the 100 simulations of the mean of a 100 simulations.*

4 THE NOVELTY BIAS

Under section 3.4 of the paper [2] two models were simulated, one working under all the assumptions made in section 2.2 and one which introduces a novelty effect. Both of these simulations yield similar results with the simulation introducing the novelty effect having as expected a larger bias but also a larger bias after adjustment. While this was done in order to prove the robustness of the proposed bias-adjusted estimator, the induction of the novelty effect as a factor of $\frac{1}{10 * U_u(t)}$ is not mathematically supported. Since this was done in order to test the proposed adjustment method, the proposed value could be increased as means of putting the proposed method to the test in more extreme circumstances. The result of these adjustments can be found in Table 3. Here it can be seen that as the bias increase so does the bias adjusted value by about an equal amount. While the bias adjusted value is lower, the effectiveness of the adjustment are relatively lower as the bias increases. It is not unthinkable that in real world applications the situation arises where the novelty factor does not lose its value as rapidly as in the proposed formula in the paper, thus lose its effectiveness.

5 JACKKNIFE VS BOOTSTRAP

At the end of section 3.4 of the paper [2] the following statement was made *"Unfortunately, we do not have an answer why jackknife adjustment works better than bootstrap under our simulated settings."* A possible explanation for this behaviour could be that the underlying statistic could be classified as a pairwise agreement measurement. Pairwise agreement measurement refers to any process where two entities are compared to see which one is preferred. A/B testing could be classified as such a case. Jackknife in general outperforms bootstrap analysis when it concerns pairwise agreement measurement [1]. While the simulation concerns Heavy user bias and not A/B testing directly the argument might not hold.

6 THE WEEKEND EFFECT

The article mentioned two factors that can effect external validity. The novelty effect and the weekend effect. The novelty effect occurs when there is an increase in interest or performance when a new technology or feature is introduced. The increase occurs not because the new feature has brought about an improvement or achievement but rather because there is an initial interest in the technology.

Table 4: Original Simulation 1 Results

Estimators	Bias and Standard Deviation
Continues Analysis	0.0211 (0.0023)
Jackknife Analysis	-0.0035 (0.0026)
Bootstrap Analysis	0.0068 (0.0024)

Table 5: Simulation 1 with Weekend Effect Results

Estimators	Bias and Standard Deviation
Continues Analysis	-0.0219 (0.0018)
Jackknife Analysis	-0.0446 (0.0021)
Bootstrap Analysis	-0.0345 (0.0020)

Table 6: Original Simulation 2 Results

Estimators	Bias and Standard Deviation
Continues Analysis	0.0341 (0.0024)
Jackknife Analysis	0.0097 (0.0029)
Bootstrap Analysis	0.0201 (0.0026)

Table 7: Simulation 2 Results with Weekend Effect

Estimators	Bias and Standard Deviation
Continues Analysis	-0.0121 (0.0022)
Jackknife Analysis	-0.0368 (0.0026)
Bootstrap Analysis	-0.0279 (0.0024)

With time the usage of the technology decreases after interest dies away.

The weekend effect is a phenomenon that occurs in many sectors. In health care it is the difference of mortality rate that occurs to patients admitted for treatment on the weekend compared to those on the weekday. In finance it deals with how the stock market returns are significantly lower. For many business however it is the case that their product is either purchased or used less on the weekend. In the article the bias-adjusted estimator was tested with a simulated novelty effect in however, no weekend effect was simulated. Therefore it was our intention to apply the weekend effect to both simulation one and two to observe the effect that it had on the bias-adjusted estimator. The weekend effect was simulated by decreasing the probability of the product being used by one half for both weekends for the two weeks that the simulation took place. So for day 6 and 7 as well as 13 and 14 there was lower probability of the product being used for both treatment group and control group.

We can see from the tables 4 to 7 that the weekend effect caused the biases to be negative. Furthermore the for both simulations the standard estimator performed similarly or even better with the weekend bias, whereas the heavy-user bias adjusted-estimator performed significantly worse. This behaviour could be problematic for real world use cases of this estimator.

7 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, we investigated the reproducibility of the results from [2] as well as the possible shortcomings of the proposed bias-adjusted estimator. In comparison to many other publications and maybe due to the relative ease of creating simulated experiments in contrast to conducted ones, the results of this paper were easily reproducible. This was possible through the sprawling availability of the source code for the simulations. The reproduced results confirmed the ones reported. Our second focus was verifying whether the bias-adjusted estimator for heavy-user bias in A/B testing would perform good in real life instances. For this we simulated experiments with two well known biases, that occur during A/B testing, the novelty bias, which was also treated in [2], as well as the weekend bias. The results of the weekend bias simulations suggests, that for an untreated occurring weekend bias, the heavy-user bias adjusted-estimator performs worse, than the unbiased estimator. For further testing of this hypothesis, experiments with the adjusted-estimator in empirical data-sets is needed.

REFERENCES

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A FIGURES OF SECTION 3.3

Figure 3: Spread of mean bootstrap adjusted estimator in simulation 1

Figure 1: Spread of mean in simulation 1

Figure 2: Spread of mean jackknife adjusted estimator in simulation 1